

Gate Current Stress for Detecting Neutron-Induced Degradation in SiC Power MOSFETs

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Abstract—Atmospheric neutron-induced degradation of SiC power MOSFETs was observed through accelerated gate stress tests. The results show that below catastrophic failure voltage conditions, devices still suffer from the effects of atmospheric radiation and long-term reliability degradation. Irradiated devices exhibit early failures in stress tests indicating gate oxide weakening due to neutron impact. The implications of the observed early failures on radiation qualification and lifetime prediction are discussed.

Index Terms—Power MOSFET, silicon carbide (SiC), neutron irradiation, time-dependent dielectric breakdown (TDDB), gate current stress

I. INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric radiation environment is known to pose a risk to high voltage electronics [1]. The emergence of new semiconductor materials, such as silicon carbide (SiC), as a replacement for silicon in power electronics applications has not eliminated the concern of radiation-induced failures of power electronics [2]–[5]. One of the radiation-induced failures is called single event burnout (SEB) in which a single energetic particle strike induces a localized high-current state in a device, which results in short circuit failure mode. Neutron-induced SEB is initiated by an interaction between a primary neutron and the nucleus of the device material. As a result of this interaction, a nucleus can gain energy via elastic and inelastic interactions. The newly produced energetic charged particles then generate free electron-hole pairs as they traverse the material. If the amount of deposited energy and charge by the particle and applied electric field in the device are high enough, the burnout will occur [6], [7].

Devices exposed to energetic particles can also suffer from leakage current degradation and latent damage even if no short circuit failure mode is present [8]–[10]. Those degradation modes can have an impact on the overall reliability of the system and therefore, the radiation hardness assurance must also cover these less prominent effects, as pointed out by Lauenstein *et al.* [2]. The voltage threshold for SEB can be hundreds of volts higher than the onset level of leakage current degradation and latent damage [9]. Especially the gate oxide reliability issues will arise well below the drain voltages at where prompt destructive failures are of concern. The standard method for assessing gate oxide integrity during radiation qualification is to apply a gate voltage within the operating ratings after radiation exposure. However, this method might

not reveal the latent damages, which act as a precursor for a device failure in long-term operation.

Constant current and voltage stresses have been used in life-time assessment of SiC devices [11]–[18]. While the intrinsic reliability of the gate oxide in SiC devices is of minor concern, the overall reliability is determined by the extrinsic or early failures [17]–[19]. Recently, constant voltage stress (CVS) has been applied in assessing the proton and electron radiation-induced gate oxide weakening [20], [21]. In this work, we investigate the applicability of constant current stress (CCS) in estimating the neutron radiation-induced degradation of SiC power MOSFETs.

II. DEVICES AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The device under test (DUT) is a commercial 4H-SiC power MOSFET (Wolfspeed, C3M0350120D). A total of 106 samples were tested of which 80 were irradiated and 10 to 20 devices per irradiation bias condition were used. Neutron irradiations were performed under atmospheric energy spectrum at the ChipIr beamline of the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, UK [22]. During beam exposure, the devices were biased at $V_{DS} = 700$ V to 1000 V. DUTs were irradiated with neutron beam flux of $5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($E_n > 10$ MeV) up to 10^{10} cm^{-2} total fluence. A detailed description of the irradiation test setup can be found in [8], where a similar setup was used. To study the reliability impact of atmospheric neutron radiation, the devices were exposed after irradiation to CCS at the gate terminal ($V_{DS} = 0$ V) with currents ranging from 0.2 μA to 50 μA . Some additional tests were performed with CVS at 36 V and 37.2 V.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To study the effect of non-destructive radiation impact on the device reliability, in this paper we are focusing on the devices which did not exhibit SEB after the beam exposure. However, 1/10 and 8/20 of the devices exhibited failures during beam exposure at $V_{DS} = 800$ V and $V_{DS} = 900$ V, respectively, before the target fluence was reached. None of the 40 devices irradiated at $V_{DS} = 700$ V failed during irradiation. For the $V_{DS} = 1000$ V irradiation voltage, all 10 irradiated devices failed during the beam exposure. This trend was expected since neutron-induced SEB dependence on drain voltage of SiC power devices has been previously reported

TABLE I
TEST CONDITIONS AND FAILURES

Irradiation V_{DS} (V)	SEB / Total	Stress condition	Extrinsic / Total
700	0 / 10	2 nA	0 / 4
700	0 / 10	2 μ A	2 / 10
700	0 / 10	10 μ A	1 / 10
700	0 / 10	50 μ A	2 / 10
800	1 / 10	2 μ A	1 / 9
900	3 / 10	2 μ A	1 / 7
900	5 / 10	36 V	1 / 5
1000	10 / 10	-	-
Pristine	- / 6	2 μ A	0 / 6
Pristine	- / 10	10 μ A	0 / 10
Pristine	- / 10	37.2 V	0 / 10

in several studies [4]–[6], [8], [10]. The summary of used irradiation and stress conditions and number of failed devices is presented in Table I.

CCS was applied on both nonirradiated and irradiated, nonfailed devices. Fig. 1 shows representative gate voltage curves for each stress condition. Time-to-breakdown T_{BD} was defined as the time when an abrupt decrease in V_{GS} was observed indicating the oxide breakdown (Fig. 1a). Cumulative charge and charge-to-breakdown Q_{BD} were calculated by integrating the current over time (Fig. 1b).

A. Stress Current

Regardless of the stress current level, the oxide breakdown for pristine devices occurs around $0.3C$ to $0.4C$ of injected charge (solid lines in Fig. 1). It seems that at all of these current levels, the oxide breakdown mechanism is the same and it is charge driven. No additional failure mechanism is present at the highest current stress value, which has been observed in time dependent dielectric breakdown (TDDB) tests at high electric fields [12], [14]. For all current levels there is an increase of the voltage before the breakdown, resulting from charge trapping and associated change in the spatial electric field in the gate oxide. However, some of the irradiated devices exhibit early breakdown (dashed lines in (Fig. 1)). All breakdown events are extracted from the current stress data and are illustrated in Weibull scale in Fig. 2.

The extrinsic tails of the early failures in the failure distributions shown Fig. 2 indicate more than one failure mode within the irradiated device population. Since the neutron interaction with the target material is stochastic in nature, there are devices within the population which do not experience the damaging impact from the neutrons. Therefore, some of the devices appear to be unaffected and follow the intrinsic failure distribution. The observed early failures for irradiated devices indicate permanent latent damage sites in the devices induced by the neutron impact. Whereas the intrinsic failures seem to be charge driven, the early failures seem to occur more randomly.

Extrinsic failures are not only a concern for irradiated devices, but have been found also in nonirradiated device populations [14], [18]. Previous TDDB studies of pristine devices have shown that less than 10% of MOSFETs [18]

Fig. 1. Gate voltage evolution as a function of stress time (a) and cumulated charge (b) for different gate currents in CCS. The devices were irradiated at $V_{DS} = 700$ V. Dashed lines represent current evolution of early failed devices (extrinsic failures) while solid lines represent devices which follow intrinsic failure distribution.

and 5% of SiC/SiO₂ MOS capacitors [14] exhibited extrinsic failures. In our study, we did not observe any extrinsic failures for pristine devices, whereas 10% to 20% of failures are extrinsic for each set of irradiated devices. When the sample size is increased, we expect to observe early failures for pristine devices as well. However, even with relatively low statistics in this study, we can observe the effect of atmospheric neutron impact on the failure distributions.

The origin of the neutron-induced oxide degradation is the charge generation in the epitaxial layer by the secondary target atom induced by the primary neutron and the subsequent charge transport and electric field redistribution. It has been suggested to cause the degradation of the dielectric properties of the gate oxide [8]. It is noteworthy that the gate IV-characteristics of the devices shown in Fig. 3 do not show any increased radiation-induced leakage current which could indicate the gate oxide weakening and possible differences between the early and late failed devices. However, even very localized damage in the gate oxide layer can act as a precursor for an early failure and the damage is revealed only after longer

Fig. 2. Charge-to-breakdown distributions for devices irradiated with atmospheric-like neutron beam at $V_{DS} = 700$ V. The highlighted extrinsic tail due to early failures is observed only for irradiated devices.

Fig. 3. Gate current-voltage characteristics of one of the early failed devices (a) and late failed device (b). No increased leakage in the gate can be observed during the gate voltage sweep for neither of the devices presented here. Devices failed at $Q_{BD} = 0.0072$ C and $Q_{BD} = 0.3240$ C during $50 \mu\text{A}$ stress.

duration of the stress. Such small damage does not necessarily contribute significantly to the overall device leakage current in the IV-characterization, which could indicate the induced damage, but may be enough to initiate the breakdown during the stress.

Chbili *et al.* suggest that trap-assisted tunneling (TAT) is potentially responsible of early TDDDB failures of SiC MOSFETs. In their model, the increase of the TAT current due to defects decrease the time to accumulate the critical Q_{BD} for oxide breakdown. This can be observed as extrinsic tail in the failure distribution [18]. The defect distribution and effective thickness of the oxide have also been studied in [23], where the extrinsic failures are attributed to variation in the oxide thickness.

Fig. 4. Weibull distributions of charge-to-breakdown for pristine devices and devices irradiated with neutrons at $V_{DS} = 700$ V to 900 V. The stress current was $2 \mu\text{A}$ except for the CVS for which the stress voltage was $V_{GS} = 36$ V.

B. Irradiation Voltage

The applied drain voltage during the irradiation has been observed to have an impact on the gate degradation under 53 MeV proton radiation [20]. Since the interaction mechanisms between the target material and high energy protons and neutrons are similar, a somewhat similar irradiation bias dependence on the gate degradation is also expected with neutrons. However, the question remains whether the high-energy part of the atmospheric-like neutron spectrum, reaching up to 800 MeV, makes a difference in the degradation response. In addition, the mono-energetic proton beam used in [20] does not contain the low energy part found in the atmospheric neutron spectrum.

Failure distributions as a function of irradiation drain voltage are illustrated in Fig. 4. Gate stress for these devices was performed with $2 \mu\text{A}$ gate current. In addition to CCS, a one batch of devices irradiated at $V_{DS} = 900$ V was subjected to CVS at $V_{GS} = 36$ V. A more detailed discussion of the CVS can be found in subsection III-C. Again, we can observe 10% to 20% early failures for irradiated devices and none for pristine, non-irradiated devices. The sample size of each drain voltage condition is not large enough to conclude on potential drain voltage effect on the failure distributions but considering all the devices, the irradiation impact can be observed. Extrinsic failures are recorded for 5 out of 30 irradiated devices. It should be noted that some of the devices irradiated at $V_{DS} = 800$ V and $V_{DS} = 900$ V failed during the irradiation and therefore were not included in the stress experiment (see Table I). When an SEB occurs, the gate is also damaged and cannot withstand the voltage required in the time-dependent breakdown experiment.

C. Pristine Devices

Fig. 5 shows Q_{BD} distributions for all the pristine devices used in the stress experiments. In addition to CCS, a CVS was also applied for 10 pristine devices. A CVS of $V_{GS} = 37.2$ V

Fig. 5. Weibull distributions of charge-to-breakdown for pristine devices under different stress conditions.

was chosen based on the gate current level during the CVS. The initial gate current was approximately $50\mu\text{A}$. Due to charge trapping and electric field redistribution in the oxide, the current varies during the stress. It can be seen in Fig. 5 that the Q_{BD} is slightly lower for this stress configuration, but is still in the same order of magnitude as the devices stressed with constant current. More importantly, the devices do not show extrinsic failures but a rather similar intrinsic failure distribution with lower β compared to the CCS batch.

Several studies have discussed the applicability and characteristics of CCS and CVS in estimating the lifetime of SiC devices [12], [14], [15], [21]. However, the main focus of this paper is the radiation-induced degradation and its impact on the failure distributions. It has been shown here that regardless of the used stress condition, the radiation-induced degradation can be captured with the accelerated gate stress. Matocha *et al.* have reported that as long as the TDDB experiments are performed with a gate electric field below 8.5 MV cm^{-1} , the breakdown occurs via the same mechanism regardless of the voltage applied across the oxide [12], [17]. In our experiments, the gate voltage varied between 31 V to 38 V which translates to 6.2 MV cm^{-1} to 7.6 MV cm^{-1} while assuming 50 nm oxide thickness.

D. Overall Radiation Impact

As we have observed in previous sections, the cumulative charge for the breakdown is not significantly affected by the stress condition used. For overall comparison between irradiated and pristine devices, we combine all the previously presented breakdown data in Fig. 6, which shows Q_{BD} distributions for all irradiated and pristine devices used in this study. Of the 55 irradiated devices included in the stress experiment, 8 experienced early failure, while none of the 26 nonirradiated devices did. Fig. 6 shows two failure populations for irradiated devices. By treating these two populations separately in Weibull analysis, we extract the β parameter of the two-parameter Weibull function fitted in these two populations.

Fig. 6. Charge-to-breakdown for all devices at different irradiation and stress conditions. Red and blue symbols represent irradiated and pristine devices respectively. Dashed lines are the 2-parameter Weibull functions fitted in the respective failure populations.

Since the neutron interaction with the target material is a stochastic process, some of the parts within the irradiated batch remain unaffected by the radiation impact and show intrinsic failures ($\beta = 6.7$) and overlap with the nonirradiated device distribution ($\beta = 5.1$).

For the early failed devices, $\beta = 0.2$, which indicates infant-mortality among the batch of devices. Those devices suffer from defects created by the neutron impact during the beam exposure while being voltage biased. The created damage could be attributed to single event gate rupture (SEGR) -like event which has been studied for Si-based power MOSFETs [24]. Either the secondary particles generated by the primary neutron interaction cause damage through the plasma column and subsequent lowering of the critical electric field of the gate oxide, or the free charge carriers generated by the ionizing secondary particles in the drift layer, are transported in the device volume, causing transient electric field increase across the gate oxide layer. These two mechanisms are referred to as dielectric response and epitaxial response, respectively [24]. It should be noted that the structure of SiC MOSFETs differs from their Si-based counterparts at least in the thickness of the epitaxial layer and consequently in the electric field in the blocking state. Therefore, especially the epitaxial response could be different between the technologies. Also, the damage observed in this study is latent and no indication of SEGR was observed during the neutron beam exposure nor in the post-irradiation IV-characterizations.

The observed radiation-induced early failures presents a challenge to lifetime prediction of the SiC devices. Especially, when operating in harsh radiation environments, the bimodality of the breakdown distribution of irradiated devices should be taken into account. One approach would be to fit a bimodal Weibull distribution to the breakdown data and carefully extract parameters for each mode as well as their respective fractions. This has been reported by Degraeve *et*

al. for 11 nm oxides on silicon [25] and also proposed by Cheung for SiC power MOSFETs [19].

IV. CONCLUSION

Radiation-induced latent damage in SiC power MOSFETs was captured by using accelerated gate stress. The observed early failures during post-irradiation stress experiment indicate a potential issue for the long-term operation of the devices in radiation environments, even if devices are operated at voltages at which SEB should not be an issue. Due to the nondestructive neutron impact, the gate oxide integrity is compromised. This was demonstrated through the accelerated gate stress test, which shows early TDDB failures for devices irradiated with atmospheric-like neutron beam at 58 % of their maximum rated drain voltage. The observed early failures raise concerns about whether current radiation qualification procedures for power electronics are sufficient to ensure SiC-based system reliability over its expected lifetime. The absence of failure during radiation exposure, and even the absence of failure during post-irradiation IV characterization, does not necessarily mean that the reliability of the device has not been affected by radiation exposure. Moreover, the increased number of early failures within the device population adds complexity to lifetime extrapolation in accelerated stress testing. We observed that the mean Q_{BD} is not affected by the stress current and the extrinsic failure tail in the Q_{BD} distribution caused by the neutron radiation impact can be seen with the used stress current levels ranging from 2 μ A to 50 μ A and irradiation voltages ranging from 700 V to 900 V.

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